

A Pilgrim's Perspective:

Arabs and Muslims in Middle English travel accounts

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Abstract (50 – 100 words):

The period between the crusades and the reformation can be seen as a golden age of pilgrimage. A number of Middle English texts deal with pilgrimages to the biblical sites which were at that time located on Islamic territory. The aim of this paper is to focus on the depiction of the “Saracens” (as the Arab Muslims were called in Europe).

Introduction

The time between the crusades and the reformation can be seen as a golden age of pilgrimage. In addition to places in England, pilgrims also set out for sites as far away as Santiago de Compostela, Rome and Jerusalem (Severn 2019: 330). Jerusalem has been seen as the center of the world since the times of the Old Testament; in the Middle Ages, it was seen as the navel of the world by authors such as Isidore of Seville amongst others. In the later Middle Ages *mappaemundi* were centered around Jerusalem (Kukita 2005: 194). It is not surprising that the places mentioned in the New Testament became the focal point of Christian theology. However, to reach these places pilgrims had to leave the realm of Christianity and venture into Islamic territories. The Holy Land surrounding Jerusalem had been an Arabic speaking country since the spread of Islam in the 7th century, in the Middle English period it was ruled by the Mamluks¹. However, Christian pilgrims were constantly entering the country to visit places like Bethlehem and Jerusalem. In fact pilgrimage to the Holy Land became increasingly popular in the 15th century; 100 years after the crusades pilgrimage to places in the Middle East had become less dangerous (Shuffelton 2008: 542).

Eyewitness accounts about Muslim lands were rare in the early Middle Ages. Only two such reports date from the Old English period, both of which are in Latin: firstly, the report of a Gaul called Arculf was written down in Latin and known to the Anglo-Saxon scholar Bede, who produced an abbreviated version, also in Latin. Secondly, the Anglo-Saxon St. Willibald (c. 700-87), who spent several years in the Holy Land, also had his story written down (in Latin). However, upon returning to Europe he stayed in Germany rather than in England, which is why his report remained unknown there (Scarfe Beckett 2003: 45). The later Middle Ages saw an increase in pilgrimages to Jerusalem as well as an increase in such travel reports; a list of Middle English travel accounts is provided by Zacher (printed in Hartung 1986: 2235-2254). MS *Wellcome Trust 8004*, is a newly found manuscript about Richard of Lincoln's pilgrimage to the Holy Land. A photographic facsimile as well as a translation into Modern English was

¹ Jews were also present in Jerusalem, but their number did not exceed 500 people at the end of the 15th century (Chareyron 2011: 120f).

published by Davey in 2013. Since this text does not feature references to Arabs, Muslims or to Islam, it will not be discussed here.

For the Mamluks and the locals of the Levante the large numbers of Christian pilgrims must have been a lucrative source of income. Pilgrimage to Jerusalem was therefore allowed but it was meticulously standardized: pilgrims had to follow specific routes when visiting the holy sites, the number of days spent at each place was also monitored by the authorities. It is therefore not surprising that travel accounts from this period are similar in their content (Davey 2013: 11). Many of these reports are very theological, the places visited are often discussed exclusively with regards to their significance in the bible. Furthermore, Europeans who wrote about Muslims were, often more influenced by the writings of earlier authors than by eyewitness accounts. Earlier texts about the Saracens continued to influence writers of the later Middle Ages and the early Modern era (Scarfe Beckett 2003: 192). Among the theories about Saracens, we find the notion that they had changed their name from Ishmaelites to Saracens so as to claim descentance from Sarah (the wife of Abraham) rather than descentance from Hager. Another theory that remained popular throughout the Middle Ages is the notion that the Saracens worshipped the Goddess Venus, an idea that goes back to the writings of St. Jerome who wrote in the late 4th and early 5th centuries (Scarfe Beckett 2003: 200). The aim of this paper is to analyze whether authors who travelled to the Holy Land had more authentic knowledge about the Islamic world. Texts that are of interest here are five Middle English descriptions of pilgrimage to Jerusalem: examples [2], [3], [5], [6] and [7]. The protagonist of Mandeville's *Travels* [1] went to many exotic places but he came to Jerusalem as a pilgrim. The unknown author of *Advice for eastbound travelers* [4] was probably a merchant but he also includes information on Islamic culture. These seven texts will be discussed below. It will then be possible to say to what extent the content of these texts can be called Orientalism as defined by Edward Said². Richard of Lincoln's account has been omitted since he does not mention the Saracens. The only other text that had to be omitted is an account extant in MS *Queens Oxf 357*, for which there is no edition (Zacher 1986: 2458). All of the texts mentioned date from the 15th century, only the Middle English translation of Mandeville's *Travels* was produced in the 14th century.

When talking about medieval inhabitants of other continents, I use modern spellings of Middle English words so as to allow the reader to locate the passage in the Middle English text. To this end the term "Saracens" is used here to refer to Arabs (i.e., Arabic speaking Palestinians) and Muslims; Christian Arabs were probably present in the Levante during the Middle Ages, but they are not mentioned in Middle English texts. The term "Moors" is used here to refer to inhabitants of medieval Iberia who had African heritage. The word "Holy Land" is used here to refer to places in modern day Israel / Palestine, which were usually visited by Christian pilgrims.

²In his introduction Edward Said (2003: 2) defines Orientalism as a Western way of studying and representing the Orient. On p. 3 he also speaks about "a Western style for dominating, restructuring, and having authority over the Orient".

Mandeville

Mandeville's *Travels* were extremely popular texts since the 14th century: about 300 manuscripts written in different European languages contain accounts of "Mandeville". However, the identity of the author has been an issue of scholarly debate. The original was probably written in French, allegedly by an Englishman. The first Middle English translation (which is extant in 32 manuscripts) was produced in the second half of the 14th century. Numerous other translations into English followed in the subsequent centuries; sensational retellings of his accounts were popular (Zacher 1986: 2239). Whether Mandeville's *Travels* is interpreted as a work of fiction or as the forerunner of modern geographical writing, it is definitely seen as one of the most widely read works on travel and geography (O'Doherty 2017: 324f). The places described are as remote – from an English perspective – as Persia, Arabia and Ethiopia. It is now clear that the author did not visit all these places, but he merely collected information from various sources (Waters Bennett 1954 / 1971: 15f).

Mandeville's *Travels* are different from all the other Middle English travel accounts: unlike all the other authors he actually engages with the cultures and religions he encounters in the east. The Egerton Version contains a chapter of seven MS pages titled *Trewþe of the Saracynes* ("The truth about the Saracens"), in which he highlights the most important aspects of Islam. Clearly, the author of Mandeville's *Travels* has read a decent translation of the Quran (which he calls *Alkoran*) as well as some other Middle Eastern and European texts about Islam. After stressing the theological similarities between Christianity and Islam, he provides an account of a private conversation between him and the *sowdan* (i.e., the Sultan) who *spakk Fransch wonder wele* (i.e., he spoke French very well) (Seymour 2010: 77). The author then argues that the Saracens are more pious than the Christians since they (the Saracens) follow their religion more carefully. This passage is quoted below, the translation is my own.

[1] And þan me tho3t grete schame þat Sarzenes whilk hase nowþer ri3t beleue ne parfite lawe schuld þus reprove vs of oure inparfitenesse and kapez þaire vayne lawe better þan we do þe lawe of Ihesu Criste, and þai þat schuld be turned thurgh oure gude ensauple to þe faith and þe lawe of Ihesu Criste, þai er drawn away thurgh oure wikked liffig. And þerfore it is na wonder if þai calle vs synfulle and wikked, for it is sothe. Bot þai er ri3t deuote in þaire lawe and ri3t trewe and wele kepez þe comaundementz of þaire Alkoran whilk Godd sent to þam by his messangere Machomete, to wham as þai say þe aungelle Gabrielle spakk oft tymes and talde him þe wille of Godd (Seymour 2010: 77).

[And then I felt great shame because the Saracens who have neither the right believe nor the perfect law should thus remind us of our imperfections and keep their worthless law better than we do the law of Jesus Christ and they that should be turned through our good example to the faith and law of Jesus Christ, are drawn away by our wicked living. And therefore, it is no wonder if they call us sinful and wicked for it is true. But they are very devout in their law and very faithful and they keep the commandments of their Koran, which God sent to them by his messenger Mohamed to whom as they say the Angel Gabriel often spoke and told him the will of God].

This amount of understanding and admiration for customs and religions encountered in the east is striking, given the fact that crusades were still fought half a century before Mandeville's *Travels* were written. Waters Bennett (1954 / 1971: 73) remarks that anti Islamic rhetoric is present in some of Mandeville's sources such as Vincent of Beauvais, Jacques de Vitry and William of Tripoli; however, Mandeville chose to omit such polemic rhetoric. Furthermore,

there is a distinct contrast between Mandeville's argumentation and the usual Islamophobic rhetoric of the Middle Ages: Mandeville's chapter on the Saracens is in stark contrast to the writings of authors such as Reginald of Canterbury, who lived and worked around 1100. In his biography of St. Malchus, Reginald portrays the Saracens as primitive and violent idol worshippers. Like many other authors of his time, Reginald relied on Jerome's *Vita Malchi* which was written in the pre-Islamic period (Scarfe Beckett 2003: 195-7). Examples for authors from different European counties who sought to refute Islam in the Middle Ages can be found in Chareyron (2011: 114ff). The level of understanding and tolerance toward Islam, that is evident in Mandeville's *Travels*, might be surprising when compared to other authors but it is in line with Mandeville's treatment of other faiths in general. Throughout the *Travels* the author proves to be a well read and tolerant individual whose personal piety does not result in intolerance with regard to other faiths (Waters Bennett 1954 / 1971: 5).

Mandeville's lengthy conversation with the Sultan (be it fact or fiction) is even more remarkable if it is compared to the writings of Felix Fabri, a German speaking traveler and pilgrim of the 15th century. When in Cairo, Fabri avoided looking at the Sultan Qaitbay so as to distance himself from Islam (Schröder 2019: 283). Mandeville, by contrast, does not show any fear of being seen as a friend of the enemy.

William Wey

William Wey, a priest and fellow of Eton College, travelled to Jerusalem in 1458 and 1462. He was given permission, in an official letter by Henry VI, to go on pilgrimage to the Holy Land (Wey 1857: I - IV). He also produced a map of the Holy Land which is 7 feet long and 16,5 inches wide, showing not only Jerusalem and Bethlehem but also places like Damascus and Gaza (Wey 1857: XV-XVII). In addition to drawing a map, Way also wrote a book about the journey, which is extant in *MS Bodl 2351*; it was printed in 1857. Besides chapters in Latin, the book also contains advice for pilgrims written in English prose. These pages are a surprisingly honest account of things that could happen during a journey to the Holy Land: Way mentions the possibility of dying from the corrupt air and water at Famagusta, Cyprus as well as fellow pilgrims who might steal water on the galley. He also advises the reader to bring their own supplies onto the galley since the patron (i.e., the person who takes them across the Mediterranean Sea) might give them poor bread and stinking water. Wey also recommends bringing a barrel that can serve as a close stool in case the pilgrim gets so sick, that he cannot come out into the open air. He also warns the reader of different fruits that can be bought on harbors along the way since they might cause a bloody flux that is potentially fatal. The Saracens are mentioned only once: the relevant passage is quoted and translated below:

[2] Also take goyd hede of yowre knyves and other smal thynges that ye ber apon yow, for the Sarsenes wyl go talkyng wyth yow and make goyd chere, but they wyl stele fro yow that ye haue and they may (Wey 1857: 7)

Take good care of your knives and the other small things which you carry on your person. The Saracens will walk with you, taking and being friendly, but they will rob you of anything you have which they can manage to steal (Davey 2010: 28f)

Unlike the author of Mandeville's *Travels*, Wey does not portray the Arabs as morally upright: in his account they are friendly but dangerous. Wey does not comment on the religion or the customs of the Saracens – his instructions written in Middle English are obviously meant to offer concise practical advice for pilgrims. Nevertheless, the medieval reader might view the natives of the Levante with some skepticism after having read the lines quoted above in example [2]. The fact that later pilgrims copied extensively from William Wey shows that

his book was remarkably popular. It should be noted that Wey also recommends a certain amount of skepticism towards the Europeans, the pilgrim is likely to interact with. Nevertheless, it seems that he was extra careful with regard to Muslims, and he had little sympathy for Islam. This can be seen in one of his Latin chapters where he describes the prophet Mohammed as a false traitor (Davey 2010: 75).

William Wey does not provide any information on how he communicated with the Saracens. His *Itineraries* feature an English – Greek wordlist and a Greek – Latin wordlist as well as a Latin – Hebrew wordlist but no information on the Arabic language (Wey 1857: 102 - 116). Cooper-Rompato (2011: 225-227) argues that Wey did not expect pilgrims to interact with Arabs who were considered heathens due to the fact that many of them were Muslims. Arabic was, however, not the only language, that was associated with Islam. When reaching a place called Axtis, William Wey received news that the Turks (i.e., the Ottomans) had been defeated in Wallachia, he also mentions the news, that the Turks had succeeded in conquering the Peloponnesus (Wey 1857: XIII f). For William Wey, Muslims were a potential hindrance to the pilgrims: due to a war between the Sultans of Babylon (Egypt?) and Damascus, Wey was unable to visit the Jordan River and Quarantania (Wey 1857: XIVf). William Wey's account was widely read by later pilgrims. This is obvious given the fact that later travel accounts contain passages that are taken from Wey's report. E.g., the author of *Informacon for Pylgrymes vnto The Holy Londe* (De Worde 1498) contains passages which are taken verbatim from William Wey (see example [7] below).

Margery Kempe

Margery Kempe needs to be briefly discussed as a person before analyzing her *Book*. She was a middle-class woman coming from a wealthy family in King's Lynn, England; she was born in 1373 and she became the mother of 14 children. When she was in her late thirties, she claimed to receive divine revelations for the first time. After ending the sexual relationship with her husband, she began to see herself as married to God. Kempe was a controversial religious figure: people were divided over the authenticity of her revelations. In the course of her forties and sixties she performed pilgrimages to various places in Europe and the Middle East. She also pursued the project of writing an autobiography, which was lost for many centuries before it was rediscovered in 1936. *The Book of Margery Kempe*, as her autobiography is called today, has received a lot of scholarly attention ever since. It is seen as the first autobiography of an English woman (Windeatt 2000 / 2004: 1-31). However, Margery Kempe was not the first woman with extraordinary spiritual gifts: the (later) Middle Ages saw a number of women from different countries who claimed to have visions and receive revelations from God. Information about their lives was sometimes written down in the form of an autobiography (Windeatt 2000 / 2004: 9-18).

The Book of Margery Kempe is attested in *British Library Additional MS 61823*; this MS, which is also known as the *Butler-Bowdon MS*, was acquired by the British Library in 1980. Produced in the mid 15th century, it is an early copy but not the original dictated by Margery Kempe (Windeatt 2000 / 2004: xvi). It is a detailed autobiography (more than 400 pages in print) written in the third person, that also mentions her journeys to Rome and the Holy Land. As the rest of the book, these travel accounts are very theological – things not related to Christianity are given little attention. Upon visiting the religious sights in the Holy Land she would often break down and cry loudly. Her companions reacted by being annoyed as a result of such repeated episodes of religious extasy. However, the passage quoted and translated below emphasizes that she had good relations with the locals (Europeans as well as Arabs).

[3] And the Frerys of the Tempyl mad hir gret cher and yovyn hir many gret relykys, desiryng that sche schuld a dwellyd stille amongs hem, yf sche had wold, for the feyth thei had in hir. Also the Sarazines mad mych of hir and conveyd hir and leddyn hir abowtyn in the cuntre wher sche wold gon. And sche fond alle pepyl good onto hir and gentyl, saf only hir owyn cuntremen (Windeatt 2000 / 2004: 174)

The friars of the Temple made her great cheer and gave her many great relics, desiring that she should have dwelt still amongst them if she would, for the faith they had in her. Also, the Saracens made much of her, and conveyed her, and led her about the country wherever she would go; and she found all people good to her and gentle, save only her own countrymen (Butler-Bowdon 1936 / 1940: 116).

The *Book of Margery Kempe* contains only a few sentences about Saracens. Where they do occur, they are portrayed as friendly people who help the author. Interestingly, it is mentioned, that Margery Kempe communicated with the Arabs by way of *tokens* (i.e., signs): when Margery had difficulties climbing the Mount of Temptation, she asked her companions for help but they “seyd ‘nay’, for thei coud not wel helpyn hemselvf” (Windeatt 2000 / 2004: 173). When a Saracen entered the scene “sche put a grote in hys hand, makyng to hym a token for to bryng hir on to the Mownt” (Windeatt 2000 / 2004: 172f). The Saracen then took her under his arm and helped her up the Mountain. Interestingly, the Saracen is described a *welfaryng* which is rendered ‘well-favoured’ by Butler-Bowdon (1940: 115); however, the MEC offers the translations “good-looking, fair, handsome”. The pilgrimage to Jerusalem can be found in the middle of *The Book of Margery Kempe*. Kukita (2005: 197) argues, that the intention was to emphasize the supposed fact that Jerusalem is located at the center of the world. The pilgrimage to Jerusalem doubtless has a central role in Kempe’s autobiography given the fact that she announces her mystical marriage with God after the completion of this pilgrimage to the Holy Land.

The benevolent attitude of the Saracens towards Margery is mirrored by her compassion for people of other faiths: Margery Kempe does not only pray for her fellow Christians but also for Jews and Saracens (Kukita 2005: 204). In this regard she is more inclusive than all the other authors discussed here who do not pray for people of other faiths.

Advice for eastbound travelers

This text by an anonymous author is attested in MS *Cotton Append viii*, ff 108b – 112 dating from the 15th century (Zacher 1986: 2457). It was edited in 1885 by C. Horstmann. The author seems to have traveled to various places in North Africa and the Middle East including Egypt, *Barewt* (i.e., Beirut in modern day Lebanon), Aleppo and Damascus. He advises the reader to travel with someone who speaks *Lumbard* (i.e., a form of Italian), Greek, *Sarasyne* (i.e., Arabic) and Turkish. It seems to be a brief summary of the most important facts – explanations of the things mentioned are often missing. E.g., the author mentions that “good lettres of recomendacione fro the Duke of the lordshipe of Venyse to their counseill in Egypte and Surre [i.e. Tyre in modern day Lebanon, known as *Sūr* in Arabic] werene good to be hadde” (Horstmann 1885: 279), but he does not elaborate on how to acquire such letters. He also warns that “meny temptaciouns be ther ofte seen to make a worthy man to falle, yef he medle moche hym-sef and goth oute abrode (Hortstmann 1885: *ibid*)” but he does not go into detail on any such temptation. On the other hand, the author is not shy with regards to speaking about the hardships during the journey. E.g., he talks about the bad quality of the drinking-water “on londe or in the see, wher water will sone stynke and wex full of worms” (Horstmann 1885: 280) and he mentions the need for laxatives. The author of *Advice* was probably a merchant rather

than a pilgrim, but it will be worthwhile to focus on what he wrote about Islamic culture. The passages below contain advice on interacting with locals. Translations are my own.

[4.1] Do faire fere with youre-self and alle youres: for englissh men have but litell love in meny parties, but yef hit be for their money or the better of gouernance (Horstmann 1885: 280).

[Make sure to travel by yourself and all your [companions] for English men have but little love in many parts [of the world] except for their money or the better “governance”]

[4.2] Yet in Surre moste ye be war to speke or dispice eny thyng of Makamet the Sarasynes proffite; for yef men do, they moste renneye or be ded; and the same, yef a man holde vp his fynger rechelesly, or be founde in eny of her Temples (Horstmann 1885: 282).

[In Tyre you must avoid speaking of or disrespecting Mohamed, the Saracen prophet for if you do so you must run or be dead. The same applies if a man holds up his finger recklessly or is found in any of their temples].

[4.3] Be neuere to bolde to shippe you in litell vessels in no costes of the hethene, for drede of suche Courssaries as bene aforeseid, as well of the Cristene as well of theyme nought of oure beleve, in euery partie of the see (Horstmann 1885: 284).

[Never be bold enough to travel in a little vessel near the coasts of the heathens for fear of such pirates as described above, be them Christians or of other faiths, in every part of the sea]

Example [4.1.] is interesting because it says that Englishmen have but little love in many regions; sadly, there are no reasons mentioned. In Example [4.2.] the reader is warned not to talk ill about “Mohammed, the prophet of the Saracens” once they are in *Surre* (i.e., Tyre in modern day Lebanon, the city is called *Ṣūr* in Arabic). Interestingly this warning is not mentioned with regards to any other city on Muslim territories such as Aleppo, Damascus or Alexandria. The reader is also advised not to hold up their finger “recklessly”, but there is no explanation as to what is meant here. The passage probably refers to the Islamic custom of lifting the index finger of the right hand while saying the testimony of faith; in *Advice* Christian travelers are advised not to imitate this gesture. Finally, the reader is warned against entering a “temple” i.e., a mosque. It should be noted that the author also warns the reader about certain customs in Europe: he mentions that many Germans are rude, and some are malicious, lacking honor (Horstmann 1885: 277). It seems that the Autor of this text was an experienced traveler who has learned not to trust anyone too quickly. He was most likely a merchant. The intended reader seems to be a noble man who is in charge of a group of people; it should be borne in mind, that people usually travelled in groups so as to protect each other.

It seems that the author has not only been to the Holy Land but also to places in modern day Syria. He describes Damascus as “a faire cite and a place of good eire, and meny sotill and precious thynges be wrought thereynne” (Horstmann 1885: 282). About Aleppo he says that “þe Cadies dwellyng“ is in that city. He describes the *Cadi* as „chief of Mamentes lawe, & a gret lord“ (Horstmann 1885: *ibid*). It is striking how well informed the author is: a *qāḍī* is indeed a judge and an expert on Islamic law. It is also worth noticing the mention of Muḥammad, who is called *Mament* in this text.

An account printed by Purchas

Another anonymous 15th century travel account is of interest here even though no manuscript containing this text has survived. However, it was printed in 1625 as part of the 4 vols set *Hakluytus Posthumus or Purchas His Pilgrimes*; a reprint in 20 vols was published 1905-7. It is an account in verse describing the Spanish rout to the Holy Land. The text can be found in vol 2, pp 1230 – 1255 in the 1625 edition and vol 7, pp 527 – 572 in the 1905 edition. The author mentions that the people don't use tables but that they sit on the floor when they eat (Purchas 1905 vol 7: 530) which is in line with the traditional Arabic way of eating. However, the author mentions, that the same custom can also be found in Ireland. Upon passing through a place, he calls "Pont Wederez", he mentions that there are many Jews and Saracens, and he acknowledges that it is "a plentifull contraye as man maie gon" (Purchas 1905: 532). With regards to other places in Spain he says that "the araie of wymmen is wonder to see, how thei be revelet about the knee" (Purchas 1905: 533). [trans: the fashion of women is wonderful to see, how they are revealed about the knee]. Obviously, this pilgrim was not merely interested in holy sites but also in the women and the way they dress. During his trip through Spain, the author eventually enters Muslim territory: as the Reconquista was not completed at that time, places in southern Spain were still under Muslim rule. The author mentions that the land is bare, "full of heeth (i.e. uncultivated land) and honger" (Purchas 1905: 534). About the local Saracens and Moors, he writes that "ever in her spicery thei be workant", referring to the fact, that spices played a more important role here than in England. About the Moors he writes that they "go alle mest naked" (Purchas 1905: 535), referring to the fact that less clothes were worn in the hot climate of Andalusia. He describes Seville as a paradise, mentioning the fruits and spices that are cultivated there. From these brief comments, it seems that the author intended to portray the Muslim territories as an undesirable place but that he could not help noticing the luxury of these cities. It is possible that for this Englishman travelling south, prejudices against Islamic civilization clashed with the reality on the ground. The passage below talks about Saracens of the Iberian Peninsula.

[5] Porta hit is the ferst place.

And Rota a nother Haven, to the See it gase:

And Serethiez a Cite full faire.

But the Sarasanez hit don apaire.

That is the untest Citie of that Lond

Toward the Sarasanez, I understand

And Cordua on that other side,

Wit Sarasanez muche soro thei abide (Purchas 1905 vol.7: 535-6).

In the passage quoted above, the Muslims are portrayed as a destructive force; they are - in this text - a constant treat in an otherwise beautiful country: the author mentions that *Serethiez* is a beautiful city, but he adds that the Saracens ruined it. About *Cordua* (i.e., Cordoba), the author says, that the city has suffered from the Saracens; however, he does not mention in which regard it has suffered. The author then describes the way through France and Italy to the Middle East. When describing the Holy Land, his report becomes increasingly theological: places are mentioned only with regards to their significance in the bible, the locals are not described.

The text discussed here is entirely written in verse; the intention might have been to make the text more popular by making the reading more enjoyable. The text can therefore be seen as

an example for infotainment, since the intention of the author is to both inform and entertain. When describing western Mediterranean regions, the author of the report quoted above [5] even describes the beauty of the local women, a detail, one would not necessarily expect to be included in the report of a religious pilgrim. However, our unknown author is not the only one to feature such episodes: Felix Fabri, a 15th century Dominican monk who lived and worked in southern Germany, went as far as describing the lascivious dance of young women in Egypt. It should be noted, though, that these episodes are part of Fabri's criticism of Islam, a religion that is obscene according to him (Schröder 2019: 277f).

The Stations of Jerusalem

This poem is extant in two MSS.: *Bodl 6922 (Ashmole 61)*, ff 128a – 135b and *Huntington Libr HM. 144 (Huth 7)*, ff 67a – 80b, both of which date from the late 15th century (Zacher 1986: 2460). It was edited in 1881 by C. Horstmann and in 2008 by George Shuffelton based on MS *Ashmole 61*; a scan of MS *Huntington Libr HM. 144* can be found online³. The author of the poem is unknown, both MSS mentioned above are larger collections of Middle English texts: while MS *Huntington 144* contains Middle English poetry and prose by different authors as well as some passages in Latin, MS *Ashmole 61* contains only Middle English poetry. *The Stations of Jerusalem* (henceforth *Stations*) describes a journey from Venice across the eastern Mediterranean to Jaffa which is today a part of Tel Aviv. The author then describes the way to Jerusalem, Bethlehem, Jericho, the Dead Sea, and the Jordan River. Instead of describing the reality of medieval Palestine, the author focusses on the religious significance of the places described. Shuffelton argues, that this text could have been written by someone who “had no direct experience of the Holy Land at all” (Shuffelton 2008: 548). He also points out, that it was primarily intended for arm-chair pilgrims, who wished to take a virtual tour through the Holy Land. It is certainly true, that the text discussed here is not a practical guide like the work of William Wey: the intended reader of *Stations* would have the possibility to get some of the benefits associated with the Holy Land while staying in their hometown. *Stations* contains a few passing comments on the Saracens which are quoted below.

[6.1] And after this a Zarysen com,
And callyd us in be a treyn.
When he hade don, he went hys weye,
And lokyd the dore with a keye (Shuffelton 2008: 323 [lines 105-8]).

[6.2] Than durst I sey that blyssed lond
Schuld duell in Crystyn mennys hond (Shuffelton 2008: 338 [line 379f]).

[6.3] On the mourne, at undren of the deye,
A Saryzen bad us gon our weye (Shuffelton 2008: 338 [line 397f]).

While on first glance it seems that the Saracens are portrayed as a threat to the pilgrims, it has to be borne in mind, that pilgrimage to the holy sites in Jerusalem was supervised by the Muslim authorities. Example [6.1.] could be interpreted as a story about the pilgrims being led into a trap by a Saracen; ME *treyn* can be translated as ‘guile’ or ‘fraud’ (cf. *train* in the MEC). However, Shuffelton (2008: 553) argues, that Muslim officials usually locked the pilgrims into the Church of the Holy Sepulcher over night. Interestingly this passage is omitted in MS

³[iif.biblissima.fr\[online\]](https://iif.biblissima.fr/online)

[https://iif.biblissima.fr/collections/manifest/c7848d41bd1fed02b0af37c3a5bf7359f61fa800?tify={%22pages%22:\[144\],%22panX%22:0.286,%22panY%22:0.255,%22view%22:%22info%22,%22zoom%22:1.383}](https://iif.biblissima.fr/collections/manifest/c7848d41bd1fed02b0af37c3a5bf7359f61fa800?tify={%22pages%22:[144],%22panX%22:0.286,%22panY%22:0.255,%22view%22:%22info%22,%22zoom%22:1.383})

Huntington 144. The reason might be that the passage was confusing even for medieval readers. In Example [6.2] the author expresses his wish that the Holy Land should be governed by Christians. Interestingly, this short passage is the only instance in all seven texts discussed here, that calls for European rule over Oriental territories. Example [6.3] mentions, that the pilgrims were asked to leave after they had spent the night in the Church of the Holy Sepulcher. This is in line with the fact that Christian pilgrimage was supervised by the Muslim authorities.

Saracens are mentioned in two other passages of *Stations*: in lines 459 – 462 (Shuffelton 2008: 340) the Saracens who are buried outside the city gate are called *cursyd creatore* (cursed creatures). It is clear that the author of *Stations* despised Muslims for theological reasons. However, it seems that Christian pilgrims valued the advice of the local Arabs: lines 790 – 792 (ibid p. 347) mention that nobody dared to touch the Dead Sea “for Zarysins that ther duelle Seys that it is the pytte of helle”.

It is also interesting to compare *Stations* to the account printed by Purchas (see example [5] above), which is also composed in verse. While *Stations* is merely a theological treatise, the account printed by Purchas features graphic descriptions of marvels witnessed along the way. Descriptions of exotic things witnessed in far away countries were also a vital part of other medieval reports about pilgrimage. Examples include Konrad Grünemberg (died 1494), Mandeville (see example [1] above) and Arnold of Harff (died 1505) who wrote about exotic customs and unfamiliar landscapes among other things (Schröder 2019: 277). Possibly, reading *Stations* could be a tedious task not only for modern readers but also for a Medieval audience.

The Ynformacion

This text is extant in MSS *London. Harley 2333* and *Oxford. Queen’s College 357*. The latter MS was edited by Brefeld (1985) who dates the text to a time between 1480 and 1526 based on the content (Brefeld 1985: 135). Both codices contain the same five texts; *The Ynformacion* makes up 34 of the 96 folios in the Oxford codex. The text at hand was written by an anonymous author, it was given the title *The Ynformacion* by Brefeld (1985: 134). When speaking about his pilgrimage to the Holy Land, the author also mentions *Sarassons* (i.e., the Saracens), *Arabions* (i.e., Arabs), the *psawdan* (i.e., the Sultan), the *Machamytistes* (i.e., the Muslims) and the *Turkis* (i.e., the Turks). Interestingly the author distinguishes between Saracens and Arabs, the latter term obviously refers to Bedouin Arabs in this context.

[7] And so from Rames we depart glali about nonetide with the patrone and the seid strenghte of Sarassons for in that waie communile is grete feere of Arabions, which with pavilions meove from place to place and ar bestialle people lieving with fructis, herbis, and roots (Brefeld 1985: 138).

In the above passage the Saracens are portrayed as protecting the pilgrims from the Bedouin Arabs who roamed the land as nomads living in *pavilions* (i.e., tents). *Rames* is identified by Brefeld (1985: 137) with Ramla, a city that lies between the Mediterranean coast and Jerusalem. Throughout the text, the Saracens are depicted as faithful subjects of the Sultan whose job it is to monitor and protect the Christian pilgrims. The term *Machamytistes* is used as a synonym of Saracens. By contrast, the Turks are portrayed as frightening enemies. It seems that *The Ynformacion* was written before 1517 when the Holy Land was conquered by the Ottoman Turks; on the expansion of the Ottoman empire see Könemann (2009: 339). Before 1517 The Holy Land had been part of the Mamluk Empire (Könemann ibid). Brefeld (1985 135) points out that *The Ynformacion* was written after 1480 since the destruction of the Italian port town Otranto is mentioned on f. 40. Otranto was destroyed by the Ottoman Turks in 1480 (cf. Brefeld 1985: 135, footnote 5).

Informacon for Pylgrymes vnto The Holy Londe

The first edition of this book was printed in 1498 by De Worde, an apprentice of Caxton's. New editions were printed in 1515 and 1524; a reprint was published in 1893 (De Worde 1893: xvii). The book features chapters in Latin as well as chapters in English, large parts of this book are taken verbatim from the *Itineraries* of William Wey (see [2] above). This is also the case with the passage quoted below.

[8] Also take gode hede to your knyves & other smale Iapes that ye beere uppon you for the Sarrasyns wol go talkyng bi you and make gode chere; but they woll stele from you yf they maye (De Worde 1893: page numbers are missing).

Page numbers are missing in the 1498 edition, nor are they provided in the 1893 reprint which is merely a facsimile of the original. The warning that the Saracens will steal from the pilgrims was included in William Wey's *Itineraries* and it was repeated in the passage quoted above [7]. It should be noticed, however, that several pages are taken from this earlier source.

Nevertheless, the author of *Informacon* also provides information that cannot be found in Wey. A striking example is a chapter titled "Here foloweth the langage of Moreske and of other countrees also" which features an English – Arabic wordlist as well as an English – Greek wordlist and the numbers in Turkish. It should be borne in mind that the Holy Land had been an Arabic speaking country since the spread of Islam in the 7th century; in the later Middle Ages these places were part of the Mamluk empire, which was ruled by a Turkish dynasty. The author of *Informacon* must have been in situations where it was necessary to communicate with the locals. The English – Arabic wordlist is only one page long (and thus significantly shorter than the Greek wordlists), but it includes helpful words and phrases such as the words for wine, water, meat and fish, as well as greetings such as "good morning" and "good evening". It also tells the reader how to ask "how much?" It is not known how de Worde put together this wordlist; as pointed out by Cooper-Rompato (2011: 232), the English – Arabic wordlist seems to be a transliteration rather than a transcription. However, given the fact that similar books dating from the 15th century feature even longer wordlists for Arabic, he could have also copied from a written text. Most of the Arabic words provided by de Worde are accurate and recognizable for Arabic speakers today; some of the words seem to be Egyptian Arabic (Cooper-Rompato *ibid*) which is relatively similar to Palestinian Arabic. From a linguistic perspective the Arabic dialects can be seen as different languages but Arabic speakers are one linguistic community since they all write in formal i.e. classical Arabic. It is interesting that the words provided in *Informacon* are spoken i.e., informal Arabic rather than classical i.e., formal Arabic. The fact, that with regard to Turkish only numbers are featured, suggests that interactions between European pilgrims and Turks was even more limited than interaction between Europeans and Arabs. Rompato (2011: 234-6) mentions the possibility that the Turkish numbers were merely included as a curiosity.

Conclusions

The later Middle English period can be seen as a golden age of pilgrimage. English pilgrims would often visit shrines in Britain, but some ventured as far as St. Iago de Compostela and Rome. However, the most significant religious sights – from a Christian perspective – were located outside of Europe: the biblical sites in modern day Israel / Palestine were the geographical focal point of (medieval) Christian theology. In the 14th and 15th centuries visiting these places meant entering Islamic territory as the Levante was ruled by the Mamluks, an Islamic dynasty. The language that was most widely spoken there (among local Christians and among the Muslims) was Arabic. Contacts between European pilgrims and local "Saracens" (as

the Arabic speaking Muslims were called in Europe) were rare and often superficial. However, a number of Middle English texts do contain information on such encounters. From the passages analyzed above it seems that Europeans pilgrims were traveling with Arabic guides after landing at Jaffa. At least this can be seen from the *Itineraries* of William Wey [2] and from *Informacon* [7]. It also seems likely that pilgrims bought provisions from their Arabic guides: *Informacon* [7] lists a number of words for foods. Other than that interaction was probably rare: the pilgrims were usually interested in the holy sites and their theological significance rather than in the land and its inhabitants; at least this can be inferred from their writing. When interactions with the locals did become necessary, the language barrier must have made communication difficult. The need for an interpreter is mentioned by the unknown author of “Advice for eastbound travelers” [Examples 4.1 – 4.2]. Mandeville claims to have spoken to the Sultan in French but this might actually belong to the realm of fiction. Margery Kempe seems to have communicated successfully by way of signs and gestures. The English-Arabic wordlist featured in *Informacon* [7] shows that pilgrims also tried to communicate with the local Arabs: many of the words mentioned are actually recognizable as spoken Arabic.

The Muslims who lived in the Holy Land are depicted as the enemy in many of the texts discussed above. Mandeville’s *Travels* is an exception since the author does not engage in the anti Islamic rhetoric that was widespread during the Middle Ages. Indeed, the author of these texts was surprisingly well informed about Islam, and he shows great admiration for the piety of the Muslims. The only (truly) English author who portrays Muslims in a similarly positive light is Margery Kempe (see Example [3]) whose positive depictions of the Saracens serve the purpose of exposing the bad behavior of her countrymen. An entirely different narrative is found in the texts of William Wey who portrays Mohamed as a false prophet and the Muslims as thieves. The merchant who wrote the texts quoted as examples [4.1 – 4.3] advises the reader not to insult the prophet Mohamed and not to enter a mosque. Medieval readers of these texts must have felt that Islam is a rather hostile faith. Accounts in verse quoted as examples [5] and [6] merely include a few passing comments about the Saracens who are portrayed as a threat to the pilgrims or as allowing only certain rites to be performed. Since the Middle English texts discussed above represent the Orient in a specific way, the term Orientalism as defined by Edward Said might be used to describe the intention of the authors. However, only one of the seven authors discussed above (the author of *Stations*, see example [6]) claims that the Orient ought to be ruled by Europeans. The term Orientalism therefore cannot fully be applied to Middle English literature about pilgrimage.

A Muslim perspective of the Europeans is not featured in the works of English travelers. One of the few passages that give us an idea of how Europeans were seen by locals in the Middle East can be found in the writings of a French traveler known as Thénau. From his brief account it appears that European Christians were considered poor, living “on roots and wild fruit, like wild boar” (Chareyron 2011: 125). Thus, it seems that stereotypes about other continents were as widespread in the Middle Ages as they are now. Traveling to other parts of the world did not necessarily lead to a deeper understanding of the local culture: the fact that pilgrimage was standardized as well as the language barrier and preconceived notions about the “enemy” meant that pilgrims to places in the Middle East did not get very close to Islamic culture. Many of the stereotypes held by medieval authors might sound far fetched to modern readers. Studying these texts might therefore allow us to question our own opinions about other cultures.

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